

Traditional Medicinal Plants' Importance of Human Welfare

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The core of traditional medical practice is the use of medicinal plants or herbs. Herbal remedies originated in various places of the world under different names. The methodical study of therapeutic herbs and their botany is known as herbalism, primarily on its medical applications. The study of traditional medicine is known as ethnomedicine. Researchers distinguish and identify different active compounds found in medicinal plants. The core of Ayurveda and its therapies is comprised of Indian medicinal plants, often known as Ayurvedic medicinal plants. When applied properly and in accordance with fundamental principles, they have astounding results. Their function extends beyond only treating illnesses; they also benefit the human body. As such, the term “elixirs of life” is aptly applied to Ayurvedic medicines. From ancient times until the present, Ayurvedic herbs have been an integral part of Ayurvedic treatment. Even the Sumerian civilization, which existed before recorded history, used therapeutic plants. In Sumerian culture, therapeutic plants were recorded in clay tablets. They listed roughly a hundred therapeutic herbs. About 800 therapeutic plants were recorded by the ancient Egyptians in “Ebers Papyrus.”

The Chinese pharmacopeia of medicinal plants, known as “Shennong Ben Cao Jing,” assisted Chinese traditional healers in treating patients. Greek physician “Dioscorides” penned “De materia medica,” a pharmacopeia of medicinal plants that listed 600 species and their varied combinations that were effective for therapies. The earliest systematic botany text was written by Aristotle and his pupil Theophrastus, and it is titled “*Historia plantarum*.” It was the first botanical book to classify plants into organized groupings. Many traditional medical systems have been evolved in India. The well-known Sidha and Ayurveda are often referred to as the Indian System of Medicine. Ayurvedic and Sidha treatments are fundamentally based on the use of medicinal herbs and herbo-mineral combinations. Medicinal plants classified as Ayurvedic Medicinal Plants that are found in Ayurvedic text books or under Ayurveda.

Medicinal plants were categorized in Ayurvedic writings based on their qualities and use. There was a list of about 800 therapeutic plants.

Medicinal plants have been used for medical purposes since ancient times. It is estimated that before herbalism, there were roughly 50,000. The 5,000-year-old Sumerian culture was the first to exhibit written history. Because many current medicine chemicals are sourced from plants, herbalism may be able to apply modern standards of effectiveness testing to herbs and medications produced from natural sources. It is also known as paraherbalism, phytotherapy, or phytomedicine. Dietary supplements made from herbs that fall within the phytotherapy category. Owing to its low cost, herbal medicine is used by 80% of people in Asia and Africa, according to the World Health Organization. In the USA, over 25% of medications are made from medicinal plants. 7,000 medicinal chemicals that are now identified from herbs, together with 120 active compounds. You can utilize a single plant or a combination of plants. It was ready in several ways. There are several options available, including alcoholic preparations, dry powder, tea, decoction, tinctures, and preparations with oil or ghee. It is thought that by seeing the sick animals, traditional healers became interested in herbal treatment.

Ethnomedicine is the study or comparison of traditional medicine used by different ethnic groups, which is based on bioactive compounds found in plants and animals. The instruments used in ethnomedicine are medical anthropology and ethnobotany. The goal of the study is to find and create a medicinal product that can be sold. Yu, a chemical substance termed “Artemisin” that is beneficial in treating malaria, was identified from Chinese medicine.

Phytochemicals. These are chemical substances that plants produce as a byproduct of metabolism; they might also be a defense mechanism. The three basic types of phytochemicals are terpenes, glycosides, and alkaloids. Alkaloids are substances with an unpleasant taste; some examples are morphine, atropine, scopolamine, hyoscyamine, caffeine, cocaine, and ephedrine (Ephedra). Medicinal herbs like Alexandrian senna, cascara, and rhubarb contain anthraquinone glycosides. Several chemical classes include polyphenols, which are helpful defenses against plant diseases and predators. Astringent tannins and phytoestrogens are two examples. Resinous plants, like conifers, contain terpenes and terpenoids.

Cultivation: Conventional or conservative agricultural methods may be used in cultivation. Rotation is advised by the World Health Organization. To achieve acceptable yields, research on soil type, climate, temperature, and humidity is required. The idea that medicinal plants are safe is naive.